

COMPARING PROMINENT PERIODICITY DETECTION ALGORITHMS TO DETERMINE A SUPERIOR METHOD

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MOTIVATION/OBJECTIVE

The motivation behind our research is to compare the Lomb-Scargle (LSP) and Conditional Entropy (CE) period finding algorithms with each other. While there have been previous comparisons of these algorithms, there are little to none that have compared them with exoplanet data. Our aim is to determine which method is more accurate in detecting periods of transit curves.

METHODOLOGY

1. Used python to create our own data as it is known for its simplicity and well-documented astronomy-based packages.
2. Coded various synthetic periodic signals, closely expressing a transit curve to test out both methods varying different factors such as signal-noise ratio, period and number of transits.
3. Used a prior that resembles the Kepler data and created our own database for the input variables.
4. Fed our input data to both periodicity detection algorithms and recorded our findings.
5. The LSP was taken from Astropy's implementation and CE was taken from cuvarbase

DATA

For our input data, we took a generic sinusoidal function and removed each peak by replacing every value > 0 with 0 to resemble a typical exo-planet transit curve. Red noise is ignored, however, we add white noise similar to those seen in ground based observation.

PLOTS

Figure 1: This is the input data of 100,000 values that we use for comparing both algorithms, we create a similar orbital distribution among exoplanet candidates found by Kepler.

Figure 2: This is a comparison between the signal to noise ratio of each input signal for both algorithms versus the Mean Absolute Deviation which has been calculated with the given formula:

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - m(X)|$$

Figure 3: We calculate the Signal to Noise Ratio with the given formula: $SNR_w =$

$$SNR = \frac{depth}{\sigma_w} \sqrt{n}$$

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

RESULTS

We find that in figure 2, although CE poses higher error at SNR of < 2.5 compared to the LSP, CE is more accurate than the LSP at higher SNR values from SNR > 2.5 .

In Figure 4 and 5, we can see that based on the average deviation, CE is slightly more accurate than the LSP. The difference between both median absolute deviations is also significant.

Overall, CE was better as it was more accurate, however, for signals with a lower SNR, LSP would be a better choice.

In regards to the LSP, when looking at multiple planets from low-high SNR, the signal produced is not exactly sinusoidal which isn't what LSP typically looks for, thus, it will be harder for LSP to find the individual period of all planets separately. The error on each planet would be higher than what it would be for a single planet.

Although CE was more accurate than LSP, we must consider that we are only using synthetic data to compare both algorithms, so results may vary/change based on real data.

In the future, we plan on adding real exoplanet data to our comparison and also expanding our comparison by using other newer implementations such as Machine Learning.

Acknowledgment:

I would like to thank Tokyo Academics for helping me on this project and for mentoring me through my work. They are an organization that tutors students and help them conduct research. This would not have been possible without them.

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